

Author Contributions

Manuscript title : **Human Rights v Diplomatic Immunity: the Khashoggi Murder Case**

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Author declaration

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Potential conflict of interest exists:

We wish to draw the attention of the Editor to the following facts, which may be considered as potential conflicts of interest, and to significant financial contributions to this work:

The nature of potential conflict of interest is described below:

No conflict of interest exists.

We wish to confirm that there are no known conflicts of interest associated with this publication and there has been no significant financial support for this work that could have influenced its outcome.

2. Funding

Funding was received for this work.

All of the sources of funding for the work described in this publication are acknowledged below:

Ministry of Education and Culture, Republic of Indonesia. The grant number is: B/1176/E3/RA.00/2020, 23 November 2020.

No funding was received for this work.

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The Corresponding Author declared on the title page of the manuscript is:

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We understand that this author is the sole contact for the Editorial process. He/she is responsible for communicating with the other authors, including the Corresponding Author, about progress, submissions of revisions and final approval of proofs.

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- Contributed data or analysis tools
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